

Limiting apparent molar volumes, their temperature derivatives and viscosity *B*-coefficients for some alkali-metal chlorides in aqueous tetrahydrofuran mixture

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Manuscript received 16 February 2001, accepted 31 May 2001

Density and viscosity of lithium chloride, sodium chloride and potassium chloride have been measured in tetrahydrofuran (THF) + water mixture (60%, w/w) at different concentrations and at 303, 308, 313 and 318 K. From density data apparent molar volumes have been derived and analyzed using Masson equation. The limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_v^0) and slope (S_v^*) are interpreted in terms of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions, respectively. The viscosity data have been analyzed using Jones-Dole equation. The structure-making/breaking capacities of the salts have been inferred from the Hepler's and Sharma and Ahluwalia's criterion.

Thermodynamic investigations play an important role in understanding the type and extent of the patterns of molecular associations that exist in liquid mixtures and their sensitivities to variations in composition, temperature, pressure and chemical nature¹. The limiting apparent molar volume of a salt is an important thermodynamic property. Since viscosity is a property of the liquid which depends upon the intermolecular forces, the structural aspects of the liquid can be inferred from the viscosity of solutions at different concentrations and temperatures. In the present work, we have carried out a systematic study on the limiting apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v^0), experimental slopes (S_v^*) and *B*-coefficients of alkali metal chlorides MCl (M = Li, Na, K) in tetrahydrofuran (THF) + water mixture (60%, w/w) at 303, 308, 313 and 318 K.

Results and Discussion

The experimental values of densities (ρ_0), viscosities (η_0) and relative permittivities (*D*) of tetrahydrofuran + water at 298 K are not available at the relevant compositions. Their available values are therefore, plotted against the mole-fractions of tetrahydrofuran, and the values at all the desired compositions have been generated from the smooth master curves and are given in Table 1. The results reveal that η_0 of the solvent mixture (THF + H₂O) increases rapidly to a maximum at about 0.143 mole-fraction or 40 wt% of THF and thereafter decreases. Such characteristics in the viscosity vs composition curve is a manifestation of strong specific interaction² between unlike molecules predominated by hydrogen bonding interaction.

The apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) were calculated from the density of the solution using eqn. (1),

$$\phi_v = M/\rho_0 - 1000 (\rho - \rho_0)/c\rho_0 \quad (1)$$

where *c* is the molarity of the electrolyte solution, *M* the molecular weight of the solute and ρ and ρ_0 are the densities of the solution and solvent, respectively. The limiting apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v^0) were calculated by the Masson equation³.

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v^* c^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where S_v^* is a constant dependent on charge and salt type and can be related to ion-ion interactions and ϕ_v^0 is the limiting apparent molar volume which is related to ion-solvent interactions. The plots of ϕ_v against $c^{1/2}$ were linear in

Table 1. Density (ρ), viscosity (η_0), relative permittivities (*D*) and specific conductance (L_0) for tetrahydrofuran + water at 298 K

Wt.%	x_2	<i>D</i>	ρ_0 g cm ⁻³	η_0 cP	$10^6 L_0$ $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$
0	0	78.54	0.99797	0.8903	1.01
20	0.059	57.25	0.98668	1.4900	3.20
40	0.143	44.50	0.96640	1.7321	2.60
60	0.273	32.00	0.94600	1.4904	1.35
80	0.500	19.50	0.91592	0.9237	1.18
100	1.000	7.58	0.88072	0.4630	0.81

all cases and from the intercept and slope one can obtain the values of ϕ_v^0 and S_v^* , respectively. The values are given in Table 2.

The experimental S_v^* values (Table 2), at different temperatures are all large and positive in THF + water mixture (60%, w/w) for all electrolytes studied, indicating the presence of strong solute-solute interactions. This type of behavior of alkali metal chlorides and some common salts has also been observed in propylene glycol-water mix-

Table 2. Limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_v^0) and experimental slopes (S_v^0) for various salts in 60% (w/w) tetrahydrofuran + water mixture at different temperatures*

Salts	ϕ_v^0 ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)				S_v^0 ($\text{L}^{1/2} \text{mol}^{-3/2}$)			
	303	308	313	318 K	303	308	313	318 K
LiCl	-268.186 (± 0.01)	-311.532 (± 0.01)	-480.479 (± 0.02)	-641.178 (± 0.01)	759.865 (± 0.01)	875.099 (± 0.01)	1301.100 (± 0.02)	1678.604 (± 0.01)
NaCl	-346.804 (± 0.02)	-371.254 (± 0.01)	-554.387 (± 0.01)	-727.152 (± 0.02)	1112.941 (± 0.02)	1144.796 (± 0.01)	1700.396 (± 0.01)	2264.464 (± 0.01)
KCl	-528.192 (± 0.02)	-561.238 (± 0.01)	-782.683 (± 0.02)	-990.201 (± 0.01)	1747.011 (± 0.01)	1835.353 (± 0.01)	2541.661 (± 0.01)	3260.971 (± 0.01)

*Standard error in parenthesis.

tures⁴. The possible explanation for the positive slopes in the studied solvent-mixture may be that the ionic association would become quite appreciable in this medium as the concentration of the electrolyte is increased thereby weakening the solute-solvent interactions. As a result, contraction of the solvent mixture would be gradually lowered with increase in concentration of the added solute. Exactly the same conclusion regarding the ion-association behavior

Table 3. Limiting apparent molar expansibility (ϕ_E^0) for various salts in 60% (w/w) THF + water mixture at different temperature

Salts	ϕ_E^0 [ml/(mol)(deg)]			
	303	308	313	318 K
LiCl	-36.264	-34.614	-32.965	-31.315
NaCl	-39.737	-37.663	-35.589	-33.516
KCl	-48.467	-45.682	-42.896	-40.111

of these electrolytes in aqueous mixtures of THF at 298 K has been drawn from conductometric studies⁵. Fuoss⁶ also found similar trends for many of the alkali metal halides in dioxane-water mixtures. The increase of S_v^0 with increase of temperature in this solvent-mixture for the studied salt suggests that more and more solute is accommodated in the void space left in the packing of large associated solvent molecules. It is also evident from Table 2 that the limiting apparent molar volumes, ϕ_v^0 are large and negative and this negative values increase as the size of the alkali metal ion increases (from Li^+ to K^+) as well as with increase in temperature (from 303 to 318). This indicates the presence of weak solute-solvent interaction and in this solvent-mixture, the solute-solvent interaction decreases from lithium chloride to potassium chloride.

Table 4. Values of *A* ($\text{cm}^{3/2} \text{mol}^{-1/2}$) and *B* ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) parameters for various salts in 60% (w/w) THF + water mixture at different temperatures*

Salts	<i>B</i> values				<i>A</i> values			
	303	308	313	318 K	303	308	313	318 K
LiCl	7.5703 (± 0.01)	7.5674 (± 0.02)	6.9095 (± 0.01)	6.3137 (± 0.02)	-3.1879 (± 0.01)	-3.1679 (± 0.01)	-2.9562 (± 0.02)	-2.6028 (± 0.01)
NaCl	7.3934 (± 0.01)	7.1393 (± 0.01)	6.7490 (± 0.01)	6.1779 (± 0.01)	-3.1465 (± 0.02)	-2.9801 (± 0.01)	-2.8421 (± 0.01)	-2.5769 (± 0.01)
KCl	5.8806 (± 0.02)	4.9455 (± 0.01)	4.9388 (± 0.02)	4.9037 (± 0.01)	-2.1897 (± 0.02)	-2.1309 (± 0.01)	-2.1157 (± 0.01)	-2.0728 (± 0.02)

*Standard errors are given in parenthesis.

The variation of ϕ_v^0 with temperature of the electrolytes in this solvent-mixture follows the polynomial equation,

$$\phi_v^0 = a_0 + a_1T + a_2T^2 \quad (3)$$

over the temperature range under the investigation. The coefficients a_i 's are determined and the following equations are obtained,

$$\phi_v^0 = 25998.407 - 136.229 T + 0.1650 T^2 \quad (4) \text{ for LiCl}$$

$$\phi_v^0 = 30900.072 - 165.397 T + 0.2074 T^2 \quad (5) \text{ for NaCl}$$

$$\phi_v^0 = 39932.144 - 217.262 T + 0.2785 T^2 \quad (6) \text{ for KCl}$$

The limiting apparent molar expansibilities, $[\phi_E^0 = (\delta\phi_v^0/\delta T)_p]$ calculated from eqn. (4–6) for different electrolytes at different temperatures are given in Table 3. It is found that the values of ϕ_E^0 increase with increase in temperature for all studied electrolytes, which can be ascribed to the presence of caging or packing effect⁷.

For determining structure-making and structure-breaking capacities of solutes in different solvents, the equation of Hepler⁸ was used,

$$(\delta\phi_E^0/\delta T) = -(\delta^2\phi_v^0/\delta T^2)_p \quad (7)$$

According to Hepler, structure-making solutes should positive value and structure-breaking solutes negative value of the term of $(\delta^2\phi_v^0/\delta T^2)_p$ respectively. It has been observed from eqns. (4)–(6) that $(\delta^2\phi_v^0/\delta T^2)_p$ for solutions of all studied electrolytes are positive, indicating thereby that

these electrolytes (LiCl, NaCl and KCl) behave as structure-makers in this solvent-mixture.

The viscosity data of solution for the electrolytes (LiCl, NaCl and KCl) in THF + H₂O mixture (60%, w/w) have been analyzed using Jones-Dole equation⁹,

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + Ac^{1/2} + Bc \quad (8)$$

where η and η_0 are the viscosities of the solution and solvent, respectively, and c is the concentration of solution. The values of A and B were calculated by the method of least-squares by fitting the experimental data in the Jones-Dole equation and these values are given in Table 4. It is evident from Table 4 that the values of B -coefficient for all the studied electrolytes are positive and large and the values decrease from LiCl to KCl as well as with increase in temperature and this behavior shows that all alkali metal chlorides (LiCl, NaCl and KCl) act as structure-promoters in this solvent-mixture system. The structure-promoting tendencies of the electrolytes are in the order : Li-salt > Na-salt > K-salt. A similar trend was reported by other workers¹⁰ in case of viscosities of perchlorates of lithium and sodium in propionic acid-ethanol mixture.

It has been reported by a number of workers that dB/dT is a better criterion¹¹ for determining the structure-making/breaking nature of any electrolyte rather than simply the B -coefficient. Table 3 shows that the value of B are positive and decreases with increase in temperature (from 303 to 318) which gives negative values of dB/dT suggesting that these electrolytes (LiCl, NaCl and KCl) behave as structure-promoters in this mixed solvent system. These conclusions are in excellent agreement with that drawn from $(\delta^2\phi^0/\delta T^2)_p$ discussed earlier.

Experimental

Tetrahydrofuran (THF; Merck) was kept several days over KOH, then refluxed for 24 h and distilled over LiAlH₄ as described earlier¹². The boiling point (66°), density (0.88072 g cm³) and viscosity (0.0046 P) compared well with the literature values¹³. The specific conductance of tetrahydrofuran was $ca\ 0.81 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 25°.

Alkali-metal chlorides (Fluka, Puris or Purum) were purified as described earlier¹⁴.

A stock solution for each salt was prepared by mass and the working solutions were obtained by mass dilution. The conversion of molality to molarity was done using density values.

Density (ρ) was measured with an Ostwald-Sprengel type pycnometer having a bulb volume of 25 cm³ and an internal diameter of the capillary of about 0.1 cm. The pycnometer was calibrated at 298, 308 and 318 K with double-distilled water and benzene¹². Viscosity was measured by means of a suspended-level Ubbelohde¹⁵ viscometer with a flow time of about 539 s. For distilled water at 298 K, the time of the reflux was measured with a stop-watch capable of recording ± 0.1 s. Details have been described earlier¹².

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